

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D5.1

Smart Border Technology Experience Research State of the Art

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Abstract:	D5.1 is a report on the smart border technology experience research state of the art. It discusses the foundations of technology acceptance assessment and modeling (TAM) and provides an overview of relevant experience factors and phenomena related to interaction with border- and access control technologies, including the experience of biometric sensing and authentication technologies. Furthermore, the TAM state of the art in those
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	application contexts relevant to the project (border control, big data analytics, and machine learning) is discussed.
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Terms and abbreviations

BC	Border Control
BCP	Border Control Point
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EES	European Union Entry/Exit System
SBC	Smart Border Control
SEM	Structural Equation Modeling
SOTA	State of the Art
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model/Modelling
TCN	Third-Country Nationals
TCNVE	Third-Country Nationals Visa Exempt
TCNVH	Third-Country Nationals Visa Holders
UTAUT	Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
BI	Behavioral Intention
IDV	Individualism versus Collectivism
NN	Neural Network

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.1 provides an overview of the state of the art (SOTA) that is relevant for the technology acceptance modeling (TAM) activities of work package WP5 of the METICOS project and related activities in work packages WP6 and WP7. Beyond discussing the foundations of technology acceptance assessment and modeling itself, a broader, user-centric perspective is given by providing an overview of relevant experience factors and phenomena related to interaction with border- and access control technologies, including the experience of biometric sensing and authentication technologies. Furthermore, SOTA in METICOS-relevant TAM application contexts (border control, big data analytics, and machine learning) is discussed.

This deliverable consists of two core parts: the first part (Section 2) provides a more general overview of the SOTA addressing human user experience of smart border technology. It gives an overview of the different groups of experience factors in the context of border control, with a focus on those aspects that are relevant to the METICOS project: access control, authentication as well as cross-cultural aspects and user diversity. The second part (Section 3) then focuses on TAM, which is also the key topic and activity of the project work package WP5. To this end, it provides a general introduction to TAM, followed by a survey of work addressing more specific aspects and challenges related to the project: application of TAM to the context of border control as well as the fusion of TAM with big data analytics and machine learning approaches.

Finally, a number of conclusions and findings from the surveyed SOTA are derived, particularly as regards upcoming activities in work packages WP5 to WP7. Among those, key findings and recommendations are:

Travelers and border guards constitute two very different border control user groups with very different requirements and perspectives on BC and related technologies. Thus, it is important to clearly distinguish between these two user groups when technology acceptance models are developed.

- One of the major influence factors on SBC system acceptability is malfunction and high error rate in document and biometrics scanning. It is important to capture such failures and consider them in TAM modeling.
- In general, many factors/parameters related to the operational environment cannot be considered when modeling technology acceptance on behalf of empirical ex-ante questionnaire data. Some of this information can be retrieved ex-post, e.g., via traveler questionnaires after the actual border control process or by analyzing responses on social networks.
- Gender-based differences in technology adoption should be investigated in the METICOS project as they help to achieve a fuller understanding of the participation and power structures between genders in society and the nature of their interaction in big data analytics.
- In METICOS, cultural dimensions should be investigated for each SBC technology of interest in order to better understand modulators in technology experience across different countries and national origins.
- There is no single universal technology acceptance model that covers every possible scenario. TAMs must be adapted to the specific contexts, technologies, user groups, research questions, etc. addressed.
- The integration of machine-learning and big data approaches in TAM represents a major research opportunity for the METICOS project. However, the project needs to ensure that selected modeling approaches also match the requirements of the use cases targeted.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

Deliverable D5.1 provides an overview of the state of art (SOTA) that is relevant for the technology acceptance modeling activities of work package WP5 of the METICOS project as well as its interactions with work packages WP6 and WP7. Beyond discussing the foundations of technology acceptance assessment and modeling itself, a broader, user-centric perspective is given by providing an overview of relevant experience factors and phenomena related to interaction with border- and access control technologies, including the experience of biometric sensing and authentication technologies. Special attention is given to the impact of human user diversity on technology experience and acceptance, members of the targeted user groups (travelers, border control staff) come from a wide variety of social, educational and cultural backgrounds.

This broader, technology-experience-based perspective forms the basis for the subsequent discussion of TAM in general as well as TAM SOTA from specific application contexts that are relevant for the METICOS project. On the one hand, this relates to applications of TAM in the context of border and access control as well as the use of big data analytics and machine learning for technology acceptance modeling. From these SOTA overviews and surveys, implications for the METICOS project are derived, including identified gaps in existing research along with promising research opportunities and directions that the project should pursue.

1.2 Document structure

After a general introduction, this deliverable provides an overview of the SOTA addressing human user experience of smart border technology in Section 2. To this end, it provides an overview of the different groups of experience factors in the context of border control, with a focus on those aspects that are relevant to the METICOS project: access control, authentication as well as cross-cultural aspects and user diversity.

Section 3 then focuses on technology acceptance modeling by first providing a general introduction to the subject matter, followed by a survey of work addressing more specific aspects and challenges related to the project: application of TAM to the context of border control as well as the fusion of TAM with big data analytics and machine learning approaches.

Finally, this document derives several conclusions (Section 4) from the surveyed SOTA and discusses resulting implications for the METICOS project, particularly as regards activities in work packages WP5 to WP7.

2 User Experience of (Smart) Border Technology

2.1 Overview / BC Experience Factors

Factors affecting user experience in borders control context might be broken down to three main layers:

- User (either passenger or border guard professional),
- Smart border control system (SBC System),
- Environment

With regards to technology acceptance modeling, environment layer is the one, which has to be carefully analyzed, as many of the acceptance influencing factors cannot be considered in final modeling. Factors like use instructions, guidance of the travelers through the airport and many others, which are often discussed in state-of-the-art research and described later in this document are impossible to be objectively considered in quantitative modeling. In user layer, it's important to distinguish between two different types of users of SBC system – passengers and border guards, as each of this group is affected by different set of experience affecting factors.

2.1.1 Border guard experience

On the opposite side to the actual passengers, automated border control system is used by border guards, and they have very different sets of effects influencing their experience with the system. Three main factors influencing border guard experience with SBC [1]:

- Usability and usefulness of the SBC system monitoring tool
- Operational environment
- Professional and personal background

All major groups influencing the general guards experience with automated border control system are depicted in Figure 1. Factors, which can be considered in the actual TAM are mainly related to the speed of the applications, speed of the entire SBC system or fluency of the border control process.

Figure 1: Factors affecting border guard experience [1].

2.1.2 Passenger experience

When passengers are approaching the point of automated border gates, many of the state-of-the-art works stress out the immense importance of proper guidance [1], [2] by creating various ways, how to introduce the functionality and requirements of the system before the actual passenger comes to it. Based on real assessments at the airports, there are many users who don't know how the system works and made no action in the automated gate due to that fact – it's important to capture those situations, and offer travelers better information on how to use the system in the future – e.g., instruct users not to move during the face recognition phase, or not to wear hats or sunglasses during the authentication process [2]. Clear signs and information about how to proceed during the border control play very important role in increasing general awareness of such systems.

Ylikauppila et al. revealed in [1], that gate design and physical appearance are the main factors affecting how easily the function of the system is recognized and usage learned.

Variance in document dimensions, materials, printing and quality of electronic and data components have an impact on the speed and accuracy of the document scanning and authentication process. Difficulties in document processing appear to the passenger often as an extended time used for the control process, and an increased number of rejections and retries. Passengers hold a wide range of different types of official travel documents. Besides passports, EU member state national ID-cards can be used for border crossing within Europe.

Demographic variables, such as passenger's age, gender and nationality, are characteristics that influence the traveler's opinion of and ability to use the system, as well as how SBC is experienced. Age, for instance, produces some physical and legal limitations. Elderly people may face difficulties due to impaired hearing or eyesight, reduced mobility or memory. Minors may not be allowed to use self-service because of legal issues. Extreme variations in height may complicate the use of physical installations. People wearing spectacles may face difficulties in the facial recognition phase, not only because the image matching may take longer but also because of the inconvenience of removing them

and trying to read instructions, etc. A large number of people prefer for one reason or another personal contact and face-to-face service, and it might be challenging to encourage those people to try out SBC systems.

It is assumed that the opportunity to use self-services for airport processes in general is more important for business travelers than those who are travelling for leisure [1].

All major groups influencing the general user experience with automated border control system are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Factors affecting passenger experience [1].

When assessing experience with SBC systems, there are important issues which need to be addressed while performing a quality assessment for automated border controlling. Users might be tired, stressed or in a rush to check through the border and therefore not willing to participate in any open-ended questionnaires [2].

One of the major concerns in the acceptance of biometrics, is the degree of trust that user gives to automated border control technology. People might not be familiar with the technology and not know to use it, or some aspects of biometric recognition technologies might be considered as intrusive by some users. To further improve user acceptance in biometrics, it has been shown that it is important to provide users with proper feedback. Typically, such feedback is offered through video, images, or symbols. Such feedback improves the usability of biometric technology – especially in cases, where user is not aware of how to use the technology, or there might be different cultural or language barriers – particularly at the airports [3].

Usage of symbols and easy to understand list of steps are also important during the whole process of automated border controls, as clear instructions speed up the whole process of check-ins, security checks and boarding at the airport, and as such, improves the acceptance rating of the whole system in overall.

Several studies investigated end users' opinions and concerns about biometric technology. Blanco-Gonzalo et al. in 2019 gathered results from such studies [3] and summarize several important outcomes related to the METICOS project:

- Biometric technologies were the preferred method of authentication, found to be more useful than other means of authentication in different contexts (access to buildings, computer authentication, financial transactions, etc.) and more useful than passwords in general.
- Users who are familiar with biometric technologies expressed several concerns about safety (collecting fingerprints, storing iris or retinal identification), or even cleanliness of the devices, an aspect receiving increasing attention due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Oostveen et al. [4] investigated and compared usability of automated border control technologies at two European airports. Study found out, that even-though automated e-gate systems have been around the airports for quite some time, they are still not utilized by passengers enough. Usability issues and unclear instructions for passengers have been identified as one of the possible sources of e-gates underutilization. As mentioned also earlier in other studies, authors again stress out the fact, that there is a need to give passengers as many instructions about how to use the e-gate system as possible, and should be provided in multiple ways, e.g., pamphlets, information via loudspeakers, information on a screen or short video clips. From the interviews with border control authorities, authors mention important insights about how different type of travelers tend to use automated border control systems: "A large part of the passenger traffic travels just once a year. The business traffic that travels more often just goes straight through. That difference is obvious."

Oostveen et al. [5] used a taxonomy developed by Wyatt in 2003, to distinguish between different groups of non-users:

- The resistors
- The rejectors
- The excluded
- The expelled

Each of these groups need different measures to transform the passengers back to "users".

The resistors of SBC systems might have doubts about the benefits of automated border controls. To teach travelers to use new technology, it is important to convince them about the ease of use and benefits of the new system.

The rejectors initially started using the technology, but later decided to stop for various reasons, e.g., malfunction, technical or human error or design issues. Apart from negative experience, users might be worried about the safety of the e-gates. The solution for convincing rejectors to use the technology again is to fix all the issues, design better interfaces for enhanced usability and increase overall appeal for passengers.

The excluded group of passengers consists of different types of passengers – disabled people on wheelchairs, passenger under 18 years old or passengers who doesn't possess sufficient identity cards/passports with embedded biometrics. To turn excluded non-users to users, various step can be taken, e.g., lowering the minimum required age, better accessibility for disabled people or creating more inclusive systems which would accept broader type range of travel documents.

The expelled group of non-users represents passengers who were able to use the system before but are unable to use it now. Reasons usually vary, one of the possible ones include damaged, defective or malfunction biometric chip inside passport. Sometimes solution to malfunctioning passport readers might be as easy as cleanup of the machine-readable zone or aerial.

2.2 Sensor and Authentication Technology Experience

Recently, user acceptance of biometric technologies has moved to other scenarios, such as mobile devices or online systems. Undoubtedly, the introduction of fingerprint sensors on mobile devices helped to further improve the general acceptability of biometric technologies. In 2017 Apple Inc. introduced Face ID in its products and doing so, brought facial recognition systems to millions of devices world-wide.

Blanco-Gonzalo et al. [3] reached several conclusions when investigating user acceptance of mobile biometrics, such as most of the participants preferred fingerprint unlock over face unlock or a PIN. Fingerprints unlock was also perceived as more secure and convenient than a PIN by most of the users.

In some border controlling scenarios – to offer more flexibility during the control process, there is a need for portable devices with biometric authentication. Research in this field [6], [7] also evaluates usability and acceptability of such technologies. According to traveler's survey performed in MobilePass project [6], 97% of the users were satisfied with the whole process, saying that authentication was quick and easy to understand. Face verification was found to be received positively by 78% of the travelers and by 16% it was considered very positive. Replacing 1-finger by contactless 4-finger authentication device further improved both reliability and acceptability of the border control procedure [7].

In the study of Oostveen et al. [4] the authors mention, that there are some quality issues with digital photographs in certain European passports. Approximately 5% of passport images contain serious deficiencies, which hinders the efficiency of facial recognition and create situations affecting user experience with automated border control systems.

Related to acceptability and satisfaction with facial recognition systems are also different types and ways how the face is scanned by the e-gate. To help position the users correctly, some systems use “digital mirror” in front of the camera, which has been found to be very effective [4]. Any inefficiencies in the system might cause serious delays, and the whole process of authentication can be slowed down from average 15-20 seconds to anything up to 5 minutes. This poses a serious problem in acceptability of the technology and might even create issues of high non-use of e-gates [5].

Another popular technology used in e-gates is iris scanning. In [8], the authors investigated the acceptability of iris scanning technology on a young group of people (ranging from 15 to 25 years old). Their research was primarily focused on the development of a technology acceptance module, and they also investigated reasons for accepting biometric electronic identification means. The paper confirms the influence of renowned technology acceptance variables such as compatibility, perceived usefulness, facilitating conditions on biometrics systems acceptance and further recommendation. The authors also prove that other factors, such as concern for privacy, trust in the technology, and innovativeness, also have an influence on technology acceptability. These all are important factors to consider when designing TAM model in METICOS project, as described in Section 3 of this document.

2.3 Traveler Handling and Access Control Technology Experience

As is already the case, air borders will account for the majority of border crossings by 2025, followed by land borders and then sea borders. Land borders are most challenging to operate in comparison with the air or sea borders. Among the challenges for the land borders there are more types of possible offence, i.e., roadworthiness, stolen vehicles, traffic offences, firearms, drugs, smuggling, driverless cars, crossings at non-designated BCPs. The new and improved land border crossings will be based on multiple integrated technologies to provide the necessary flexibility to accommodate diverse situations. Such technologies can include mobile devices for border guards, automatic number-plate recognition for recognizing vehicles, web and mobile applications for travelers, gateways for coaches and buses and facilities for trucks.

Figure 3 Breakdown of the projected number of entry and exit border crossings for Schengen countries in 2025 per type of passenger across the various types of borders (figures in millions)

Traveler processing technologies have a great impact on the travelers' experience as they transit through an airport. Travelers go through a heavy process of planning and scheduling, check-in steps, baggage management, and security clearance, which may reduce the overall satisfaction of the air travelers. [9]

There is constant demand for improving security at automated kiosk (e.g. European Union Entry/Exit System (EES) proposal [10]). In any case, according to the EU-LISA report, the higher the number of tasks that need to be performed by passengers at a kiosk are, the probability that a passenger successfully reaches the end of the process decreases and the success rates drop further when both fingerprints and facial images need to be enrolled, which is exactly the case with the new EES proposal. In addition, the report notes that more time can be saved with SBC technologies at exit as the entry checks are much more thorough and time-consuming. For example, EU-LISA tested the feasibility of enrollment kiosks at the port in Helsinki (which was a different process from the entire EES process as prescribed in the EES proposal). The result was that only 22% could successfully enroll their facial and fingerprint images to the required quality standards, while 44% could not complete the process at all. The success enrollment rate at Lisbon airport at the required standard was also low, only 33%. The kiosk usage at Madrid airport concluded that the success rate decreases when multiple biometrics are used. Thus, the feasibility of letting third-country nationals (TCNs) perform enrollment and entry checks via kiosks should be thoroughly assessed [11].

Figure 4 and Figure 5 below illustrate how TCN Visa exemptions and TCN Visa holders can have different border crossing experiences and times (see totals in bottom rows). All options that can impact on the duration of the border crossings in relation to the EES are listed, along with estimated added duration (the other details in the two figures do not matter here). TCN Visa exemptions (TCNVE) and TCN Visa holders (TCNVH) will take different times to cross the border, which is why the lists separate values for both of these categories. Note, that the first entry and subsequent entries of travelers are presented in separate figures.

Consequently, experience assessment and acceptance modeling should consider the fact that TCN Visa exemptions and TCN Visa holders will have different experiences when crossing borders. Especially crossing times for TCNs at first entry to EU creates significant influence on the overall acceptance and thus should be considered in TAM modelling. Subsequent entries also add marginal time delays and should be considered when developing TAM models.

	EES FIRST ENTRY				VISA HOLDER				VISA EXEMPT			
	CRITERIA	S	D	C	Time	S	D	C	Time			
Fingerprint identification (1:N)	N	N	N		++	-	-		20-30			
MRZ (for VH also visa sticker number)	N	N	+	0	N	N	+	0				
Additional, mandatory fields	N	N	N	60-90	+	--	--	60-90				
8 FP mandatory	N	N	N	0	++	--	--	40-60				
4 FP mandatory	N	N	N	0	+	-	-	<30 (vendor:3s)				
Photo from e-MRTD	+	N	+	0	+	N	+	0				
or Live photo	+	-	-	30	+	-	-	30				
or Photo from print	--	N	N	0	--	N	N	0				
Date, time, border crossing point, authority, etc	N	N	N	0	N	N	N	0				
Additional, optional fields	+	--	--	30-60	+	--	--	30-60				
TOTAL				120-180				170-270				

Figure 4 Impact on BCP crossing time of EES-related options (first entry) [11]. ‘Time’ columns designate duration (in minutes) added to the process by each option/step.

	EES SUBSEQUENT ENTRY/EXIT				VISA HOLDER				VISA EXEMPT			
	CRITERIA	S	D	C	Time	S	D	C	Time			
1-4 fingerprints	N	N	N	0	+	-	N	15-20				
or Photo from e-MRTD	N	N	N	0	+	-	+	15-20				
MRZ (for VH also visa sticker number)	N	N	+	0	N	N	+	0				
Date, time, border crossing point, authority, etc	N	N	N	0	N	N	N	0				
Additional, optional fields	+	--	--	30-60	+	--	--	30-60				
TOTAL				30-60				45-80				

Figure 5 Impact on border crossing duration in terms of EES-related options (subsequent entry/exit) [11]. ‘Time’ columns designate duration (in minutes) added to the process by each option/step.

2.3.1 Example: Facial recognition technology

Facial recognition is a prime example of a highly controversial smart border control technology. According to a recent survey from travel search engine [Reservations.com](https://www.reservations.com), approx. one in three Americans (32.5%) disagree with the government using facial recognition technology at airports to improve security and boarding speed.

Conversely, 42.6% of those surveyed approve of the use of facial recognition technology to improve security and boarding speed. One-quarter of Americans (24.8%) neither agree nor disagree [12]. It is predicted that by 2021, facial recognition will be in use at the top 20 U.S. airports for 100% of international passengers, including American citizens. This is according to an executive order.

From an operational perspective, a huge advantage of facial recognition is speed: with 99% accuracy, it takes two seconds to analyze a face in the system. However, security is one of the major citizen concerns, and storage of facial scans is still often the point of major discussions. While U.S. Customs and Border Protection has said, it will only keep facial exit scans for a maximum of 14 days, the rules for partner airlines vague.

“Since its inception, over two million passengers on over 15,000 flights have used the technology on exit,” the agency boasted earlier this month. By the end of 2021, U.S. Customs and Border Protection has been given the goal of scanning the faces of passengers on 16,300 flights per week.

Given the expected increase of roll-outs, it is important to obtain similar acceptance figures for Europe. And in addition to mere monitoring of acceptance, stakeholders and decision-makers should better understand the driving factors behind acceptance (including the ones mentioned above).

Figure 6 Agreement or disagreement with usage of facial recognition technology [12]

2.4 Cross-cultural aspects and user diversity

2.4.1 Gender and Diversity-related Aspects

The concept of ‘the border’ is no longer viewed primarily as static lines at the outer edge of the state, but increasingly as a mobile, bio-political sociological entity and virtual apparatuses of control [13]. Yet borders remain as symbolic sites of power that inscribe meaning about who belongs and who does not. Just as borders are diverse because of their locations and contexts, so are the individuals crossing them. Whether they are seasoned air travelers, day traders, migrants, tourists, refugees or those engaged in or victims of criminal or terrorist activity, people cross borders for a variety of purposes. Stereotypes and assumptions about different roles, responsibilities, needs and capacities have profound implications for border officers, their policing practices and therefore for the experience of those crossing borders [14].

Identity-based differences such as gender, age, disability, ethnicity, race, class and religion do not stand alone but intersect with each other in a varied and complex entanglement. They also participate in the way of how diverse bodies are to move with different degrees of freedom and influence reasons for crossing borders (i.e., who crosses them and why? Which networks do they use? what opportunities and resources do they have at their destination?) “. While some (especially those with social, economic or cultural capital) enjoy easy mobility, and continual encouragement to travel from the tourism industry or from governments that require certain types of workers for employee shortages, others find their movement continually denied and controlled” [15]. That is why aspects of diversity need to be explored in a multidimensional manner, where citizenship, cross-border migration background and bilingualism also play a vital role. Therefore, there is a strong need to situate them within a “broader ‘matrix of domination’ that includes patriarchy, racism, heterosexism, colonialism, nationalism, and other mutually constitutive systems of oppression” [16]. The intertwined effects of gender, race and

border securitization policies are particularly visible and “emerging literature calls for a more gender and race-sensitive understanding of the way that sovereign power operates” [14].

For example [17], Abomhara et al. (2020) give practical examples regarding issues with discrimination using biometric technology in border control. In detail the authors examine disability, age and religion. While people with disabilities “may refuse to or feel uncomfortable about undergoing iris scans or providing fingerprints due to permanent or temporary disability,” senior citizens and children might also have specific problems with using biometrics enrolment devices. For children under three years old, it is particularly hard capturing fingerprints due to their very small fingerprint area. When talking about Religion, visual “aspects (e.g., beard, headscarf) or interpersonal contact (e.g., photographs, touching, exposing parts of the body) may render a biometrics system an unacceptable intrusion”.

These examples demonstrate that border control experiences are always interlocking experiences between diverse bodies and technology. Mackay et al. emphasize how heavily border security relies on risk assessment, and that border management strategies reflect how countries address the challenges these assessments identify [14]. They also underline that “failing to take into account the gendered needs of those who cross borders may result in poor decision-making, affecting individuals’ rights and opportunities, and ultimately national and international security” [14].

Several Studies have observed a series of gender-related trends that include increasing numbers of women travelling both alone and as part of a family group. Therefore, integrating a gender and diversity perspective in the work of border control is essential and can have a significant impact on the ability to recognize power relations and hierarchies and to respond to the varying needs and vulnerabilities. Gender and diversity sensitive standards can play a big part in the reduction of inequalities and can help border management services to become better equipped identifying and managing security threats while ensuring the protection of the human rights of individuals crossing borders.

2.4.2 Cultural Aspects

Previous work has investigated what influence national cultural values have on technology-related beliefs and behaviors [18]. Understanding the nature of the effect that cultural differences have on perceptions of technology becomes more and more important [19]. Some speak of a moderating effect promoting that the relationship between behavioral beliefs and intentions is moderated by cultural factors, while other positions hold the assumption that technology-related beliefs and behaviors might vary with different national cultural values in specific [20]. Accordingly, for the development of our acceptance model we aim at considering cultural aspects with regard to potential influences on border control experience.

In METICOS, amongst others, we want to investigate the effect of cultural values on selected elements of acceptance of SBC systems. Taking up on the multidimensional approach in investigating the potential modulators of technology acceptance of SBCs also different dimensions of culture should be distinguished. In the last couple of decades various attempts to formalize culture or cultures have been undertaken (For a summary of cultural models, dimensions and frameworks see e.g. [21]. As one of the most prominent theoretical frameworks, however Geert Hofstede proposed cultural dimensions, namely addressing power distance, masculinity vs. femininity, uncertainty avoidance, and individualism vs. collectivism [22]. These dimensions are commonly used to predict or explain national cultural differences related to technology adoption and use:

Power distance (PD) refers to the degree to which people accept inequalities among other members of society or their social group. Previous work on the relationship between PD and aspects of technology acceptance shows that PD scores are negatively associated with the uptake of technology [23]. Cultures with high scores in PD tend to have centralized decision-making structures which might

negatively affect their technology adoption (e.g., Erumban2006). Also, Srite and Karahanna (2006) [20] identified PD as a significant moderator of the relationship between their variable of social norms (SN) and behavioral intention (BI). Regarding the model under development and the planned citizen survey in METICOS it could be assumed that technology acceptance of SBC systems is greater for people originating from high PD countries, respectively for people with high scores in the PD dimension.

The dimension of **masculinity versus femininity (MAS)** indicates that social groups with high scores in the dimension of masculinity are associated with societies with a clear distinction between the two genders. Femininity refers to societies in which there is less differentiation between the two genders. There have been attempts to associate the dimension of masculinity with positive attitudes towards technology, but findings lack empirical evidence so far [24]. Other research suggests that the relationship between perceived ease of use (PEOU) and behavioral intention (BI) is stronger for those with more feminine values (e.g., Srite and Karahanna [20]). Authors further point out that the construct of technology acceptance lacks feminine values as with dedicated expressions such as job- and performance-centered it is dominated by rather masculine values. As such, the dimension of masculinity vs. femininity should be considered when investigating cultural aspects in acceptance of SBCs.

Uncertainty avoidance (UA) refers to the level to which people feel comfortable in risky situations or situations with an uncertain outcome. Some studies have assumed a direct effect of UA on technological adoption, with high UA cultures hypothesized to be less open towards technological change (e.g., Erumban [24]). Similarly, it might be assumed that people with a high score on uncertainty avoidance will tend to be less comfortable with using SBCs as novel, unusual or unstructured situations compared to people who show low-level UA.

Finally, **Individualism versus collectivism (IDV)** refers to a spectrum according to which people take care only of their own selves or feel to belong to and care for a strong group. In previous studies countries with a high IDV score showed a higher rate of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) adoption than countries with a low ID score [24]. Regarding technology acceptance, IDV might be considered as a possible modulator in the relationship between subjective norms (SN) and behavioral Intention (BI) [20]. To explore the role of IDV on technology acceptance remains an area open to inquiry that requires further investigation.

Altogether, it is important to note that also relationships between different cultural dimensions need to be considered as confounds when investigating and modeling acceptance of ICT. Kyriakoullis and Zaphiris [19] provide an overview on studies about the impact of culture on the acceptance and usability of different technologies. For example, in relations with biometrics technologies Riley et al. found cultural differences between respondents from India, South Africa and the UK, however, without conclusive reference to the Hofstede dimensions [23]. In the content of SBC systems, to better understand modulators in technology experience across different countries and national origins, the mentioned dimensions should be investigated for each BC technology under focus.

Despite their popularity, from a psychometric point of view, the Hofstede dimensions show low validity and provide ambiguous results regarding dimensionality [25]. As one promising implication [26] concluded that national culture might not be assessed via unidimensional measures, but rather multidimensional measures should be researched and relevant psychological, individual-level cultural traits should be captured. More recently, individual measures of national cultural values have been developed for the cultural dimensions in relation with technology acceptance questions [27]. Based on Hofstede's [22] original scales, new measures provide a more appropriate individual assessment of national cultural values [27].

The consequence is that for the interrogation of individuals across different countries, individual-centered cultural orientations can be more useful and meaningful than can specificities of countries, ethnic or social groups. To better reflect culture at the individual level, in METICOS corresponding measures should be used to investigate the interplay between dedicated acceptance factors and individual cultural values.

3 Technology Acceptance Modeling (TAM)

3.1 TAM Principles, Concepts and Theories

In general, there are many models and theories about prediction, adaption and usage of technology by individual persons. One of the most famous concepts is the technology acceptance model (TAM), originally introduced by Davis in 1989 [28], based on Ajzen and Fishbein's theory of reasoned action [29]. In contrast to previous work, TAM replaces attitude measures with the two technology acceptance measures—ease of use, and usefulness. Figure 7 depicts the original TAM. According to the concept of TAM, based on individual expectations, prerequisites and demographic background and of course the design and functionality of a certain technology determine the perceived usefulness and the perceived ease of use (Note: in the first empirical evaluation in 1989 by Davis, an electronic mail program and a file editor were evaluated). According to the behavioral concepts, these two factors are the main drivers to determine the attitude of a certain person about a certain technology (Note: This relationship has been discussed and criticized by others, see [30] for a detailed overview). Furthermore, behavioral intention is affected by this attitude and by the perceived usefulness. Is the behavioral intention strong enough, the actual usage of the technology takes place.

Note, that in most of TAM-based empirical research, the *actual* usage of a certain technology is *not* part of the evaluation, i.e., behavioral intention is the main output variable and is mostly interpreted how strongly accepted a certain technology is.

Figure 7: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989) [28].

During the last decades, the original acceptance model has been adapted and revised several times. The original TAM from 1989 [28] was extended in the year 2000 by Venkatesh and Davis [30] – namely TAM2 - because the original TAM did not consider social aspects to determine adoption. Hence, the variables subjective norm, voluntariness, experience, image, and work-related variables, job relevance, output quality and result demonstrability are added. Figure 8 depicts TAM2.

Figure 8: Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) by [30].

In 2008, Venkatesh & Bala extended TAM2 with the constructs “anchor” and “adjustment” to create TAM3 [31]. The construct “anchor” includes the variables computer self-efficiency, perception of external control, computer anxiety and computer playfulness, the construct “adjustment” includes the variables “perceived enjoyment” and “objective usability”. Figure 9 depicts the concept of TAM3.

Figure 9: Technology Acceptance Model 3 (TAM3) by [31].

Because several, competing acceptance models were developed over the years, in 2003, the so-called Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was developed by Venkatesh [32]. Four constructs are identified as determining factors for behavioral intention: Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, Facilitating Conditions. Gender, Age, Experience, and Voluntariness of Use moderate the influence of the four determining factors. Figure 10 depicts the UTAUT.

Figure 10: Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology [32].

As shown, there are several competing models about technology adoption. In general, acceptance models need to be adapted depending on specific contexts, user groups, research questions, etc.:

since the perfect, ultimate acceptance model does not exist, a model needs to be developed for each scenario using the afore-mentioned theories and base models as a starting point.

3.1.1 TAM Development and Application Process

In this subsection, we describe the typical process in acceptance-related research. First, the context-specific, yet unparametrized acceptance basic model is created. Second, empirical data is collected. Thirdly, data analysis is performed (including parametrization of the model) to validate the model, which finally leads to conclusions and recommendations.

In acceptance-related research, it is common to extend and adapt common acceptance models (see previous section) based on the underlying research questions and the context of the evaluation. In the majority of TAM-related research, the factors “Usefulness” and “Easiness of use” are fixed, and the main output factor is “Behavioral Intention”. Based on the specific product or service which is evaluated, “Usefulness” is divided into several factors. For example, the authors of [33] evaluated a smart payment card applying the technology acceptance model. In this case, the factor “Usefulness” was divided into “Increased convenience”, “Decreased wallet size”, “Coolness”, “Fun”, etc. Furthermore, trustworthiness factors covering privacy & security expectations and quality & reliability expectations were added to the model. In another example, the authors of [34] split the factor “Easiness of use” into “Easiness of Installation”, “Easiness of Configuration” and “Easiness of Usage” to cover all relevant steps of a typical Smartphone App Installation process. In general, there are two ways to decide how to shape acceptance models to fit the current needs: first, doing desk research to find scientific, empirical work applying context-specific acceptance models in certain domains, and second, conduct workshops and interviews with relevant stakeholders to identify important aspects of the product or service.

Next step is to collect data based on the underlying acceptance model, which was created in the previous step. In general, qualitative and quantitative data can be collected. In early stages of product or service development, focus groups, which create qualitative output, can be conducted to validate the initial acceptance model. It is also possible to conduct (online-)surveys. For this approach, the factors of the acceptance models are transferred into question items, e.g., the factor “perceived usefulness” is represented via the questions “Using the technology would improve my performance in doing my job”, “Using the technology at work would improve my productivity”, “Using the technology would enhance my effectiveness in my job” and “I would find the technology useful in my job”. Each question is answered with a 5- or 7-item scale ranging from “not agree” to “agree”. If the survey is conducted online, the product might only be experienced via video or graphics, but no physical interaction is possible, which could have a negative impact on the validity of the results. On the positive side, online surveys can be conducted in a fast and inexpensive way. As a third option, a laboratory user study could also be executed, i.e., study participants are able to experience the product directly, and the data collection is done via quantitative questionnaires, and additionally, qualitative interviews can be conducted to get additional feedback.

After the empirical data has been collected, there are several ways for analysis. Because each factor is represented via several items, mean values can be reported for each factor, e.g., “perceived usefulness” could have a mean value of 4.2 (if a 5-point rating scale is used, the maximum value would be 5(=very useful), the minimum value would be 1(=not useful)). Furthermore, correlations between factors can be calculated to evaluate how important one specific factor is for another factor. The correlation coefficients can be used to prioritize factors, e.g., if the correlation between “Usefulness” and “Increased convenience” is lower compared to the correlation between “Usefulness” and “Coolness”, it is more important for the target group that the product is convenient instead of being experienced as cool. Additionally, multiple linear regressions can be executed to model the relation between the output variable (usually “Behavioral intention to use”) and several acceptance-related variables. With regressions, it is also possible to evaluate how much variance of the output variable can be explained via the factors available in the model, e.g., 75% of the variance can be explained.

Furthermore, it is possible to use Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), a multivariate statistical analysis technique that is used to analyze structural relationships between factors.

The results of the analysis can be used to derive specific recommendations for the development process of the evaluated product or service. For example, additional development resources can be assigned to factors with unexpected low ratings. Furthermore, the expected technology adoption is quantified, further evaluations can use this base value to check if adoption increases over time. If the variance, which is explained by multiple regression analysis, is rather low, further investigations are necessary to identify additional, yet unknown, factors affecting the acceptance. Hence, focus groups can be executed to reveal such factors. Besides valuable input for the development process, also guidelines for communication and marketing strategies can be derived from the acceptance analysis, e.g., it is possible to focus on highly relevant usefulness-aspects in the communication process to maximize the impact in the relevant target group.

Current TAM literature suggests that there is not a single, universal acceptance model that can be applied to any technology and context. Hence, acceptance modeling always requires the development and validation of specific, customized models. Furthermore, the afore-mentioned TAM development process (modelling, collection of empirical data, analysis) will be applied in upcoming WP5 tasks.

3.2 TAM in Specific Contexts

3.2.1 The use of Big Data Analytics and Machine Learning Methods in the context of TAM

Today, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is broadly accepted and has proved applicable in identifying users' willingness to utilize ICT. Moreover, Big Data Analytics and Machine Learning methods have become important globally both in academics and business, since they enable real-time data analysis to arrive at key decisions based on evidence rather than intuition. We have conducted an extensive research to identify the use of TAM combined with Big Data and Machine Learning techniques.

One of the first approaches in this field has been a study which aims to examine the behavioral intention to adopt smartwatches by individuals. After having developed the respective theoretical model, by incorporating the TAM with relevant features of smartwatches, data was collected through the form of survey, and the research model was evaluated using six popular machine learning classification algorithms. These included a meta classifier (LogitBoost), a logistic regression classifier (SimpleLogistic), a lazy classifier (KStar), a Bayesian classifier (Naïve Bayes), a rule learner (OneR), and a decision tree classifier (LMT) [35].

In order to examine the acceptance of WhatsApp stickers among university students, another study employs similar supervised machine learning classification algorithms through a wide range of methodologies such as decision trees, if-then-else rules, meta classifiers, Bayesian networks, functions, and neural networks (NNs), in order to examine the relationships among the constructs in the proposed research model. The authors used the popular statistical analysis tool Weka to analyse the data by employing the following classifiers: a bayesian classifier (Naïve Bayes), a logistic- regression classifier (SMO), a lazy-classifier (IBk), a meta-classifier (Bagging), a rule-learner (PART), and a decision-tree (Random Forest) to test the hypotheses derived from the combined TAM and Uses and Gratifications theory (U&G) model they propose [36].

A similar approach was used to test the predictive model regarding the intention to use mobile learning during Coronavirus Pandemic for educational purposes. Various different classifiers were applied, using once more the tool Weka, such as the OneR, J48, Logistic, LWL (Locally Weighted Learning), AdaBoostM1, and BayesNet classifiers, to assess the research model, which was based on the data gathered from a survey, together with Partial least squares-structural equation modelling [37].

The same classifiers applied by the same tool were used to test a novel model which extends the TAM with the expectation-confirmation model (ECM) and social influence to predict the actual use of machine-learning systems [38].

Another study treats consumers adoption behavior as a binary classification problem. The authors apply two different types of machine learning-based approaches (Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Logistic Regression (LR)) to predicate the possible action result by taking into consideration of all factors from the collected survey data. The purpose is to uncover the key factors that influence purchase intention of customers in the current online-to-offline (O2O) mobile commerce through the proposed novel model, an extended version of UTAUT [39].

Finally, another novel approach is the use of Neural Networks in order to evaluate the hypotheses in a novel proposed model. In this direction, a study extends the TAM model in order to predict mobile-based money acceptance and sustainability in developing countries and employs structural equation modeling–artificial neural networks (SEM–ANN) approach to assess the proposed model. A feed-forward-back-propagation (FFBP) multi-layer perceptron (MLP) ANN with significant predictors obtained from SEM as the input units is shown to achieve high accuracy. Indeed, the ANN is able to capture both linear and non-linear relationships among decision variables, as compared to structural models, which detect only linear relations only [40].

Compared to conventional approaches like SEM, machine learning-based approaches take into consideration of all the possible inputs and discover the more complicated relationships between inputs and output in a better way, therefore they perform better in all afore-mentioned studies. These studies have a novel contribution to the Information Systems (IS) literature since they constitute one of the first attempts to apply machine learning techniques in predicting the individuals' adoption of new technologies. Moreover, we have noticed a steadily increasing number of articles in this direction, and we believe that the use of Big Data Analytics techniques and Machine Learning in combination with the already established Technology Acceptance Model in literature and practical applications will continue to rise.

Regarding the pros and cons of each approach, with SEM the goal is generally to understand the relationships among multiple variables. For instance, it is difficult for traditional analysis methods to solve the problem involving complicated relationships, but SEM can be used to analyze the structure of the relationships among latent variables for calculating correlation coefficients [41]. However, when considering the intention to accept new technology, linear models like PLS-SEM tend to oversimplify the complexities. To solve the problem of oversimplification, the NNs can be used as a standalone method, or combined with PLS-SEM, to identify non-linear relationships [42]. The biggest difference between the two is that SEMs are easy to interpret and good for inference. On the other hand, SVMs and NNs have their limitations, the biggest of which is that they are like "black boxes" which output answers at deceptively high levels accuracy, however without indications of confidence/precision and without transparency regarding how they arrive at their predictions or classifications [43]. Moreover, NNs tend to overfit the data provided for training, which limits models' ability to generalize, often resulting in a low performance at the deployment stage.

Another approach would be to combine the PL-SEM approach with the Machine Learning – NN approach to evaluate the prediction model. This hybrid approach could be suggested as a significant methodological contribution from a machine learning standpoint, and it can be implemented to predict models with the highest accuracy [44].

All in all, prediction accuracy versus interpretability is the main crucial distinction for choosing the model and the approach which suits each individual case. In the context of METICOS, the goal is to take into account the above approaches and methodologies and examine which can be extended, in order to address the requirements of the METICOS use cases as defined in WP4.

3.2.2 TAM in the Context of Border Control Technologies

In the context of border control technologies, acceptance modelling based on TAM or UTAUT in general focuses on certain aspects of border control systems, e.g., on biometrics. In [34], the authors discuss which factors impact the behavioral intention to accept biometrics. As shown in Figure 11, according to the authors of the paper, beside common acceptance factors like perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, also trust concern for data privacy and perceived risk determine the behavioral intention to use. For a detailed overview please see also [45], [46] and [47].

Figure 11: Acceptance model for biometric technology [34].

3.3 Relevant Datasets or Databases

3.3.1 FRONTEX Guidelines and Recommendations

From an extensive literature review, we could not identify any suitable, accessible dataset that could serve as input for the TAM modeling in the context of METICOS. On the other hand, FRONTEX, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency, has issued a set of publications concerning best practices for the Automated Border Control systems, focusing both on operational and on technical dimensions. These Best Practice Guidelines (BPGs) have been drafted by the Frontex Working Group on SBC and include the following documents:

- Best Practice Operational Guidelines (BPOG) for Automated Border Control (SBC) Systems [48],
- Best Practice Technical Guidelines (BPTG) for Automated Border Control (SBC) Systems [49], and
- Guidelines for Processing of Non-EU Nationals through Automated Border Control [50].

Each document serves a different purpose and was conceived as a standalone source; however, it is recommended to be read in combination with each other.

The first document (BPOG) is structured in two main areas. The first proposes guidelines and recommendations on the operational dimension of SBC, such as its operational and functional

requirements and the implementation process and the second addresses issues related to the traveler experience, including methods for awareness-raising among travelers, to deliver usage instructions and to achieve a high-quality and user-friendly service [48].

The second document (BPTG) is structured in four main sections, which focus respectively on the physical architecture of an SBC system, the document authentication process, the biometric verification process and quality control, all from a technical point of view including recommendations and guidelines in an effort to achieve convergence in the basic technical features as well as consistent security levels at the different border crossing points (BCPs) of the European Union (EU) where SBC solutions are deployed. Moreover, the document concludes by providing guidelines on the *quality control and quality assurance* (p.50 – 53) which could constitute a basis for the data to be provided as input to the TAM. Some of the given recommendations are the following:

- As a general recommendation, it proposes that apart from successful border crossings, in the operational register anonymized data from other types of transactions should be logged as well, such as access attempts with documents not accepted by the system (e.g. non-electronic passports), access attempts with non-eligible documents (e.g., third-country nationals holding an e-Passport) and access attempts by an eligible traveler with a valid e-Passport but whose verification was not successful (e.g., due to a biometric verification error).
- Moreover, another suggestion is to store some traveler information as part of a data entry, such as nationality of the document issuer, age or age bands, and gender.
- For the document verification, the total verification time and the total access time should be stored, and for the facial verification process, some attributes suggested to be stored are the overall result of the face capture and verification process, any error messages from the face capture unit and the verification unit and the total time of the biometric verification process, including others.

For all the recommendations, we advise readers to consult the respective document [49].

The last document provides guidelines to clarify the legal, operational and technical aspects of SBC implementations aimed to facilitate TCN border crossings as they exist today and could exist in the future in line with the European Commission’s proposals to establish an entry/ exit system (EES proposal), and amendments to the Schengen Borders Code (SBC amendments) [50].

All in all, this set of reports by FRONTEX constitute an effort to promote harmonization of practice, similar traveler experience and minimum required security levels at the different BCPs where SBC systems have been deployed. In this sense, these reports constitute a starting point for identifying the availability of the data, recommended by FRONTEX, at the Border Control Points participating in METICOS project. After examination of availability, such data could be relevant for the Technology Acceptance Model developed for the acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies, and thus be fed as inputs to the model in order to validate it.

3.3.2 Interaction of Social Sensing with TAM on Data and Rules Level

METICOS WP6 focuses on social sensing, with the goal to access and assess travelers’ and border control staffs’ perceptions, emotional states and social interactions in order to understand whether a border technology will be accepted or not, or how well it will be accepted by travelers and border staff. The main goal of WP6 is to make predictions about technology acceptance, but it is not about momentarily finding out whether a technology in use is being accepted or not or how well. However, there is interaction between the social sensing toolkit and the WP5 TAM since on the one hand, the social sensing toolkit will provide some of the data that is required for TAM to make technology acceptance decisions and on the other hand, rules extracted through social sensing and rules coming from pilot partners will also be required for developing and implementing the TAM. Particularly for WP6 and WP7, we suggest using the data categories as provided in the figure below:

Figure 12: Categories of data required for Social Sensing (WP6).

One upcoming task is to find out which ones of these data categories are also required for the WP5 TAM. Secondly, rules that may be also useful for WP5 might be identified. Thirdly, the social sensing toolkit modelling and development composes of two stages and there is a need for clarifying at which stage, which type of input can be provided to TAM. Fourthly, when both models are in development, we will get the opportunity to compare the technology acceptance decision by TAM and technology acceptance prediction by the social sensing toolkit. This last point will also give us the opportunity to compare our models.

4 Conclusions and Implications for the METICOS Project

This deliverable has provided an overview of the state of art that is relevant for the technology acceptance modeling (TAM) activities of work package WP5 of the METICOS project, as well as its interactions with work packages WP6 and WP7. In the first part (Section 2), a broader, user-centric perspective was given by providing an overview of relevant experience factors and phenomena related to interaction with border- and access control technologies, including the experience of biometric sensing and authentication technologies. Special attention was given to the impact of human user diversity on technology experience and acceptance, members of the targeted user groups (travelers, border control staff) come from a wide variety of social, educational, and cultural backgrounds.

The second part is a discussion of TAM in general as well as TAM SOTA from specific application contexts that are relevant for the METICOS project. On the one hand, this relates to applications of TAM in the context of border and access control as well as the use of big data analytics and machine learning for technology acceptance modeling. From these SOTA overviews and surveys, a number of implications and recommendations for the upcoming work in the METICOS could be derived:

Automated border control experience factors:

- Travelers and border guards constitute two very different border control user groups with very different requirements and perspectives on BC and related technologies. Thus, it is important to clearly distinguish between these two user groups when technology acceptance models are developed.
- Travelers are in direct contact with human traps, biometric scanning devices and other technologies controlling their travel documents, and each of these technologies have certain impact on the overall acceptance of the SBC system.
- Border guards on the other hand are influenced by a whole different set of factors – such as fluency of the border control process and usability of the UI. The two main factors/factor groups influencing border guard experience with BC technologies are a) Usability and usefulness of the BC system monitoring tool and b) the operational environment.
- In general, many factors/parameters related to the operational environment cannot be considered when modeling technology acceptance on behalf of empirical ex-ante questionnaire data. Some of this information can be retrieved ex post, e.g., via traveler questionnaires after the actual border control process or by analyzing responses on social networks.
- It is important to take into account that when using questionnaire-based inquiries, one has to consider that many of the passengers might be tired after long travel, or nervous about the border control process.
- It is also important to distinguish between frequent and occasional travelers.

Access Control and Authentication Technology Experience:

- One of the major influence factors on SBC system acceptability is malfunction and high error rate in document and biometrics scanning. It is important to capture such failures and consider them in TAM modeling.
- The overall design (e.g., multi stage controlling, human-traps) of the SBC system has significant influence on the acceptability, but it hard to be objectively measured. It's important to capture reasons what went wrong during the authentication process, as many times the technology works correctly, but user instructions were unclear – long waiting times and high error rate in authentication process should be addressed by checking if there is technology malfunction, problematic documents - or the problems arise from unclear instructions to the travelers how to use the system.
- When assessing acceptance for gathering training data for the model, it is important to capture details about the document being used for authentication (is the photo readable, is the whole document readable, does the biometric chips work, what kind of ID document it is), in some cases also height of the traveler, disabilities, type of spectacles or contact-lenses (if there is facial recognition or iris scanning), whether the traveler wears hat/cap, luggage size, etc.

User Diversity and Cultural Background:

- Tackling the remaining blind spots regarding the topics of technology experience assessment in relation to gender and diversity, gender-based differences in technology adoption should be investigated in the METICOS project as they help to achieve a fuller understanding of the participation and power structures between genders in society and the nature of their interaction in big data analytics.
- Furthermore, in the context of border control also the discrimination experience should be assessed related to diversity aspects such as age, gender, race, religion, as well as aspects of the physical appearance.

To better reflect culture at the individual level, in the context of SBC systems, cultural dimensions should be investigated for each SBC technology of interest in order to better understand modulators in technology experience across different countries and national origins. Corresponding measures such as [27] should be used for experience and acceptance assessment to investigate the interplay between dedicated acceptance factors and individual cultural values.

TAM Theories and Development:

- There is no single universal technology acceptance model that covers every possible scenario. TAMs must be adapted to the specific contexts, technologies, user groups, research questions, etc. addressed.
- WP5 TAM development should follow the generic TAM development process presented in this deliverable: base model creation, data collection, analysis & model parametrization.
- Aspects that can (and should) be covered by the METICOS WP5 TAM:
 - Macro-Level technologies like multi/single gate, mantrap configurations, degree of automation etc. So, macro-level technologies are combinations of micro-level technologies.
 - Micro-Level technologies like iris scan, facial recognition, document readers, etc. (which often form part of a macro-level SBC)
 - User characteristics like travel habits, technology awareness/attitudes, cultural background
- Aspects that *cannot* be covered by the METICOS WP5 TAM:
 - Environmental/situational aspects like lighting, terminal atmosphere, signage, etc. [1]. This also includes impact of prospective/experienced waiting times, queues, etc. These

influencing factors cannot be reliably assessed ex-ante at scale e.g. by means of online panels.

TAM in Specific Contexts:

- Beyond traditional structural equation modeling (SEM), various attempts have already been made to use machine-learning techniques for TAM.
- However, trade-offs like prediction accuracy vs. interpretability turn model and algorithm choice into a non-trivial challenge (cf. the black-box problem). Thus, the project needs to ensure that selected approaches also match the requirements of the METICOS use cases targeted (see WP4).

Datasets & Data Collection:

- Due to the general lack of TAM datasets matching the targeted technologies and application context, the main source of METICOS TAM modeling data will result from the data collection activities performed within the project.
- In addition, a number of SBC systems related publications by FRONTEX ([49], [50] and [50]) point out relevant field data that is likely to be available at BCPs that might be relevant for WP5 TAM modeling activities (as well as WP7 activities).
- The envisaged development of the social sensing toolkit (WP6) is likely to provide further synergies with regard to acceptance prediction related data and rules.

Based on the insights we generated in this deliverable, the first draft of METICOS’ embedded technology acceptance prediction (ETAP) model is presented in Figure 13. The depicted blueprint will be enhanced and refined during project execution. Furthermore, the model is used in T5.2 “Theory Verification, User Involvement and Dataset Building” for the empirical evaluation via online surveys.

Figure 13: ETAP model draft.

5 References

- [1] M. Ylikauppila, S. Toivonen, M. Kulju, and M. Jokela, "Understanding the Factors Affecting UX and Technology Acceptance in the Context of Automated Border Controls," in *2014 IEEE Joint Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference*, The Hague, Netherlands, Sep. 2014, pp. 168–175. doi: 10.1109/JISIC.2014.33.
- [2] J. J. Robertson, R. M. Guest, S. J. Elliott, and K. O'Connor, "A Framework for Biometric and Interaction Performance Assessment of Automated Border Control Processes," *IEEE Trans. Hum.-Mach. Syst.*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 983–993, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/THMS.2016.2611822.
- [3] R. Blanco-Gonzalo *et al.*, "Biometric Systems Interaction Assessment: The State of the Art," *IEEE Trans. Hum.-Mach. Syst.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 397–410, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1109/THMS.2019.2913672.
- [4] A.-M. Oostveen, M. Kaufmann, E. Krempel, and G. Grasmann, "Automated Border Control: A Comparative Usability Study at Two European Airports," Social Science Research Network, Rochester, NY, SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 2432461, Apr. 2014. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.2432461.
- [5] A.-M. Oostveen, "Non-use of Automated Border Control Systems: Identifying Reasons and Solutions," Sep. 2014, doi: 10.14236/ewic/HCI2014.36.
- [6] R. Blanco-Gonzalo, R. Sanchez-Reillo, I. Goicoechea-Telleria, and B. Strobl, "The Mobile Pass Project: A User Interaction Evaluation," *IEEE Trans. Hum.-Mach. Syst.*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 311–315, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1109/THMS.2018.2791571.
- [7] A. Weissenfeld, A. Zoufal, C. Weiss, B. Strobl, and G. F. Domínguez, "Towards Mobile Contactless 4-Fingerprint Authentication for Border Control," in *2018 European Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference (EISIC)*, Oct. 2018, pp. 73–76. doi: 10.1109/EISIC.2018.00020.
- [8] C. Lancelot Miltgen, A. Popovič, and T. Oliveira, "Determinants of end-user acceptance of biometrics: Integrating the 'Big 3' of technology acceptance with privacy context," *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 103–114, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.dss.2013.05.010.
- [9] European Commission, DG for Home Affairs, and PricewaterhouseCoopers, *Technical study on smart borders: final report*. Luxembourg: EUR-OP, 2014. Accessed: May 13, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_executive_summary_en.pdf
- [10] European commission, "Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing an Entry/Exit System (EES) to register entry and exit data and refusal of entry data of third country nationals crossing the external borders of the Member States of the European Union and determining the conditions for access to the EES for law enforcement purposes and amending Regulation (EC) No 767/2008 and Regulation (EU) No 1077/2011," 2016. [Online]. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:19cfa4b9-fca5-11e5-b713-01aa75ed71a1.0020.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
- [11] PricewaterhouseCoopers, *Smart borders pilot project: report on the technical conclusions of the pilot. Volume 1. Volume 1*. Brussels: LISA, 2015. Accessed: May 13, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_pilot_-_report_on_the_technical_conclusions_en.pdf
- [12] reservations.com, "Survey: 43% of Americans Approve, 33% Disapprove of Facial Recognition Technology in Airports." Accessed: Mar. 03, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.reservations.com/blog/resources/facial-recognition-airports-survey/>
- [13] V. M. Basham and N. Vaughan-Williams, "Gender, Race and Border Security Practices: A Profane Reading of 'Muscular Liberalism,'" *Br. J. Polit. Int. Relat.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 509–527, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-856X.2012.00517.x.
- [14] A. Mackay, Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces, Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, Vereinte Nationen, and Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women, *Border management and gender*. 2019. Accessed: May 12, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osce.org/odihr/447049?download=true>

- [15] E. Stanley, “Reviews Borders, Mobility and Technologies of Control, Sharon Pickering and Leanne Weber (eds), Springer, Dordrecht, 2006, , 19:2, 252-253,” in *Current Issues in Criminal Justice*, vol. 19, 2006, pp. 252–253.
- [16] S. Dağtaş, “Inhabiting Difference across Religion and Gender: Displaced Women’s Experiences at Turkey’s Border with Syria,” *Refuge*, vol. 34, no. 1, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.7202/1050854ar.
- [17] M. Abomhara, S. Y. Yayilgan, A. H. Nymoan, M. Shalaginova, Z. Székely, and O. Elezaj, “How to Do It Right: A Framework for Biometrics Supported Border Control,” in *E-Democracy – Safeguarding Democracy and Human Rights in the Digital Age*, vol. 1111, S. Katsikas and V. Zorkadis, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 94–109. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-37545-4_7.
- [18] X. Li, T. J. Hess, A. L. McNab, and Y. Yu, “Culture and acceptance of global web sites: a cross-country study of the effects of national cultural values on acceptance of a personal web portal,” vol. 40, no. 4, p. 26, 2009.
- [19] L. Kyriakoullis and P. Zaphiris, “Culture and HCI: a review of recent cultural studies in HCI and social networks,” *Univers. Access Inf. Soc.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 629–642, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10209-015-0445-9.
- [20] Srite and Karahanna, “The Role of Espoused National Cultural Values in Technology Acceptance,” *MIS Q.*, vol. 30, no. 3, p. 679, 2006, doi: 10.2307/25148745.
- [21] A. Maleki and M. de Jong, “A Proposal for Clustering the Dimensions of National Culture,” *Cross-Cult. Res.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 107–143, May 2014, doi: 10.1177/1069397113510268.
- [22] G. Hofstede, *Culture’s Consequences*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications, 1984.
- [23] C. Riley, K. Buckner, G. Johnson, and D. Benyon, “Culture & biometrics: regional differences in the perception of biometric authentication technologies,” *AI Soc.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 295–306, Oct. 2009, doi: 10.1007/s00146-009-0218-1.
- [24] A. A. Erumban and S. B. de Jong, “Cross-country differences in ICT adoption: A consequence of Culture?,” *J. World Bus.*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 302–314, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.jwb.2006.08.005.
- [25] P. E. Spector, C. L. Cooper, and K. Sparks, “An International Study of the Psychometric Properties of the Hofstede Values Survey Module 1994: A Comparison of Individual and Country/Province Level Results,” *Appl. Psychol.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 269–281, Apr. 2001, doi: 10.1111/1464-0597.00058.
- [26] W. O. Bearden, R. B. Money, and J. L. Nevins, “Multidimensional versus unidimensional measures in assessing national culture values: The Hofstede VSM 94 example,” *J. Bus. Res.*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 195–203, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2005.04.008.
- [27] B. Yoo, N. Donthu, and T. Lenartowicz, “Measuring Hofstede’s Five Dimensions of Cultural Values at the Individual Level: Development and Validation of CVSCALE,” p. 17.
- [28] Davis, F. D., “Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology,” *MIS Q.*, pp. 319–340, 1989.
- [29] Ajzen, I.; Fishbein, M, *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Englewood Cliffs,; NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1980.
- [30] Venkatesh, V; Davis, FD, “A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies.,” *Management Science*, vol. 46, pp. 186–204, 2000.
- [31] Venkatesh, V. and Bala, H., “Technology acceptance model 3 and a research agenda on interventions,” *Decision Science*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 273–315, 2008.
- [32] Venkatesh, Viswanath; Morris, Michael G.; Davis, Gordon B.; Davis, Fred D., “User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View,” *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 425–478, 2003.
- [33] Lisa Diamond, Marc Busch, Valentin Jilch, and Manfred Tscheligi, “Using technology acceptance models for product development: case study of a smart payment card,” *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services Adjunct (MobileHCI ’18)*, pp. 400–409, 2018.
- [34] Sackl, Andreas; Schatz, Raimund; Tscheligi, Manfred, “Use and even Recommend? AcceptanceModeling of a Smartphone Launcher App forElderly Users,” *INTERACT 21 (submitted)*, 2021.

- [35] Arpaci, I., Al-Emran, M., Al-Sharafi, M.A., and Shaalan, K., “A Novel Approach for Predicting the Adoption of Smartwatches Using Machine Learning Algorithms,” *Stud. Syst. Decis. Control Springer*, vol. 295, pp. 185–195, 2021.
- [36] Al-Marouf, Rana A. Arpaci, Ibrahim Al-Emran, Mostafa Salloum, Said A. Shaalan, Khaled, “Examining the Acceptance of WhatsApp Stickers Through Machine Learning Algorithms,” *Stud. Syst. Decis. Control*, vol. 295, pp. 209–221, 2021.
- [37] Akour I, Alshurideh M, Al Kurdi B, Al Ali A, Salloum S, “Using Machine Learning Algorithms to Predict People’s Intention to Use Mobile Learning Platforms During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Machine Learning Approach,” *JMIR Med Educ*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2021.
- [38] Muhammad Alshurideh, Barween Al Kurdi, Said A. Salloum, Ibrahim Arpaci & Mostafa Al-Emran, “Predicting the actual use of m-learning systems: a comparative approach using PLS-SEM and machine learning algorithms,” *Interact. Learn. Environ. Routledge*, pp. 1–15, 2020.
- [39] Xinying Li, Lihong Zheng, “Consumers Adoption Behavior Prediction through Technology Acceptance Model and Machine Learning Models,” in *Statistics for Data Science and Policy Analysis*, Springer, pp. 333–346.
- [40] Gbongli, K., Xu, Y., & Amedjonekou, K. M., “Extended Technology Acceptance Model to Predict Mobile-Based Money Acceptance and Sustainability: A Multi-Analytical Structural Equation Modeling and Neural Network Approach,” *Sustain. Switz.*, vol. 11, no. 13, 2019.
- [41] Tarka, Piotr, “An overview of structural equation modeling: its beginnings, historical development, usefulness and controversies in the social sciences,” *Qual Quant*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 313–354, 2018.
- [42] Chong, A.Y.L.; Chan, F.T.; Ooi, K.B., “Predicting consumer decisions to adopt mobile commerce: Cross country empirical examination between China and Malaysia.,” *Decis Support Syst*, vol. 53, pp. 34–43, 2012.
- [43] Garson, G.D., *Neural Networks: An Introductory Guide for Social Scientists*. London, UK: Sage, 1993.
- [44] Yueling Xu, Wenyu Zhang, Haijun Bao, Shuai Zhang and Ying Xiang, “A SEM–Neural Network Approach to Predict Customers’ Intention to Purchase Battery Electric Vehicles in China’s Zhejiang Province,” *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 3164, 2019.
- [45] M. Scott, T. Acton, M. Hughes, “An assessment of biometric identities as a standard for e-government services,” *Int. J. Serv. Stand.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 271–286, 2005.
- [46] S.A. Shaikh, J.R. Rabaiotti, “Characteristic trade-offs in designing large-scale biometric-based identity management systems,” *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 342–351, 2010.
- [47] A. Taneja, A. Wang, M.K. Raja, “Assessing the impact of concern for privacy and innovation characteristics in the adoption of biometric technologies,” presented at the 37th Annual Conference of Decision Sciences Institute, Decision Sciences Institute, Bricktown- Oklahoma City, 2006.
- [48] Frontex (EU body or agency), “Best Practice Operational Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems.” Apr. 22, 2016. Accessed: Mar. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://frontex.europa.eu/publications/best-practice-operational-guidelines-for-automated-border-control-abc-systems-WJLwNL>
- [49] Frontex (EU body or agency), “Best Practice Technical Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems.” Aug. 31, 2015. Accessed: Mar. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://frontex.europa.eu/publications/best-practice-technical-guidelines-for-automated-border-control-abc-systems-3ZjKHL>
- [50] Frontex (EU body or agency), “Guidelines for processing of third country nationals through automated border control.” Mar. 11, 2016. Accessed: Mar. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://frontex.europa.eu/publications/guidelines-for-processing-of-third-country-nationals-through-automated-border-control-vm9d3t>